

A Critical Examination of Pascal's Value for the Magnetic Susceptibility of the CH₂-group.

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In a previous paper (*Phil. Mag.*, 1934, 18, 449) we had a critical examination of the susceptibilities of several homologous series and we found that the value for the CH₂-group is of the order of -11.36×10^{-6} as against Pascal's value of -12.35×10^{-6} , which when corrected for the new value for water comes out at -11.86 . It was shown that the lower value for the CH₂-group yields a value of χ_a of the order -2.68×10^{-6} as against -2.98×10^{-6} which is the figure obtained from Pascal's value of the CH₂-group. The theoretical value for χ_a is -2.37×10^{-6} and is in fair agreement with our value.

We have now critically examined Pascal's data and find that Pascal adopted the mean -12.35×10^{-6} by a study of twenty four compounds comprising seven different series. Pascal later carried out numerous investigations extending to over 80 substances in different series. As the accuracy of his later work has been generally recognised, we have included all his data in our list for a re-examination of his values.

The atomic weights employed by Pascal were slightly different from the modern atomic weights adopted by us. As the molecular susceptibilities are obtained by multiplying molecular weights with specific susceptibilities, we find that the employment of newer values of the molecular weights causes an appreciable change in the calculated value of χ for the CH₂-group. This procedure is justified irrespective of the accuracy of susceptibility measurements as Pascal would have done the same thing if the values now known to be established were accepted in his time.

The specific susceptibility of carbon as measured by Pascal with great precision from his experiments on carbon, prepared from recrystallised white sugar, was -5.2×10^{-6} . The atomic susceptibility for carbon as given by him was -6.25×10^{-6} . From this, we find the atomic weight of carbon, as taken by Pascal, was

$$\frac{-6.25 \times 10^{-6}}{-5.2 \times 10^{-6}} = 12.02,$$

instead of 12.00 which is the value adopted at present. The values for hydrogen and nitrogen were 1.008 and 14.01 against 1.0077 and 14.008 now given in the International Critical Tables. In our previous paper, as also in this one, the molecular weights of the compounds were calculated by using atomic weights now accepted as given in the International Critical Tables, 1923 Ed.

In the tables given below we have gathered together the susceptibilities of nearly all the compounds useful for these determinations and examined by Pascal in his monumental work.

TABLE I.

Hydrocarbons.

	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$.	Pascal's value $\chi_{CH_2} \times 10^{-6}$.	Corrected value $\chi_{CH_2} \times 10^{-6}$.
Aliphatic.			
Hexane, C_6H_{14}	-79.6	-12.05	-12.02
Octane, C_8H_{18}	-103.7	-13.00	-12.99
Decane, $C_{10}H_{22}$	-129.7		
Aromatic.			
Benzene, C_6H_6	-57.4	-12.50	-12.49
Toluene, C_7H_8	-69.9	-12.20	-12.18
1:3-Xylene, C_8H_{10}	-82.1		
Diphenyl, $C_{12}H_{10}$	-108.7		
Diphenylmethane, $C_{12}H_{12}$	-120.0	-11.30	-11.27
Unsaturated.			
*Styrolene, C_8H_8	-71.0		
* α -Methylstyrolene, C_9H_{10}	-83.4	-12.40	-12.38
* $\alpha\beta$ -Dimethylstyrolene, $C_{10}H_{12}$	-94.5	-11.10	-11.07
Trimethylethylene, C_5H_{10}	-56.4		
Octylene, C_8H_{16}	-93.2	-12.26	-12.23
Diallyl, C_6H_{10}	-57.4		
Dimethyl-2:4-hexadiene, C_8H_{14}	-81.9	-12.25	-12.20

* These names have been changed in the present nomenclature as : Styrene, α -methylstyrene and $\alpha\beta$ -dimethylstyrene.

TABLE II.
Oxygenated compounds.

	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$.	Pascal's value $\chi_{CH_3} \times 10^{-6}$.	Corrected value $\chi_{CH_3} \times 10^{-6}$.
Alcohols.			
Ethyl alcohol, C_2H_6O	-35.7	-12.20	-12.17
Propyl alcohol, C_3H_8O	-47.9	-12.26	-12.25
Octyl alcohol, $C_8H_{18}O$	-109.2		
<i>iso</i> Butyl alcohol, $C_4H_{10}O$	-61.6	-11.70	-11.67
<i>iso</i> Amyl alcohol, $C_5H_{12}O$	-73.3		
<i>tert</i> Butyl alcohol, $C_4H_{10}O$	-61.7	-12.10	-12.08
<i>tert</i> Amyl alcohol, $C_5H_{12}O$	-73.8		
Acids.			
Formic acid, CH_2O_2	-20.70	-12.20	-12.18
Acetic acid, $C_2H_4O_2$	-32.90	-12.40	-12.37
Propionic acid, $C_3H_6O_2$	-45.30	-12.70	-12.70
Butyric acid, $C_4H_8O_2$	-58.00		
<i>iso</i> Butyric acid, $C_4H_8O_2$	-59.20	-11.30	-11.28
<i>iso</i> Valeric acid, $C_5H_{10}O_2$	-70.50		
Aldehydes.			
Acetaldehyde, C_2H_4O	-23.00	-12.40	-12.37
Propionaldehyde, C_3H_6O	-35.40	-12.30	-12.28
Butyraldehyde, C_4H_8O	-47.70	-12.20	-12.19
* Amyl aldehyde, $C_5H_{10}O$	-59.90	-12.50	-12.48
Enanthyl aldehyde, $C_7H_{14}O$	-84.90		
Ketones.			
Acetone, C_3H_6O	-35.1	-12.40	-12.35
Methylethyl ketone, C_4H_8O	-47.5	-12.40	-12.40
Methylpropyl ketone, $C_5H_{10}O$	-59.9	-12.10	-12.04
Methylbutyl ketone, $C_6H_{12}O$	-72.0	-12.60	-12.56
Methylhexyl ketone, $C_8H_{16}O$	-97.2		
Esters.			
Methyl acetate, $C_3H_6O_2$	-45.5	-12.00	-11.95
Ethyl acetate, $C_4H_8O_2$	-57.5		
Methyl bromoacetate, $C_3H_5O_2Br$	-74.1	-12.30	-12.29
Ethyl bromoacetate, $C_4H_7O_2Br$	-86.4	-12.10	-12.04
Methyl acetate, $C_3H_6O_2$	-45.5		
Methyl propionate, $C_4H_8O_2$	-57.6		

* Present nomenclature : *iso*Valeraldehyde.

TABLE III.
Halogenated compounds.

	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$.	Pascal's value $\chi_{CH_2} \times 10^{-6}$.	Corrected value $\chi_{CH_2} \times 10^{-6}$.
Propyl chloride, C_3H_7Cl	-58.1		
		-12.32	-12.28
Octyl chloride, $C_8H_{17}Cl$	-119.7		
Ethyl bromide, C_2H_5Br	-55.5		
		-12.00	-11.93
Propyl bromide, C_3H_7Br	-67.5		
isoPropyl bromide, C_3H_7Br	-67.8		
		-12.30	-12.25
isoAmyl bromide, $C_5H_{11}Br$	-92.4		
Acetyl chloride, C_2H_3OCl	-40.3		
		-12.20	-12.19
Butyl chloride, C_4H_9Cl	-64.7		
Ethylene chloride, $C_2H_4Cl_2$	-62.1		
		-12.33	-12.31
Amylene chloride, $C_5H_{10}Cl_2$	-99.1		
Ethylene bromide, $C_2H_4Br_2$	-82.5		
		-12.30	-12.28
Amylene bromide, $C_5H_{10}Br_2$	-119.4		
		-12.43	-12.35
Octylene bromide, $C_8H_{16}Br_2$	-156.7		

TABLE IV.
Nitrogenous compounds.

	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$.	Pascal's value $\chi_{CH_2} \times 10^{-6}$.	Corrected value $\chi_{CH_2} \times 10^{-6}$.
Methylamine, CH_5N	-28.1		
Diethylamine, $C_4H_{11}N$	-63.5		
isoButylamine, $C_4H_{11}N$	-64.2		
		-12.48	-12.45
Di-iso-butylamine, $C_8H_{19}N$	-114.1		
		-12.30	-12.26
Tri-iso-butylamine, $C_{12}H_{27}N$	-163.3		
isoAmylamine, $C_5H_{13}N$	-77.0		
		-12.32	-12.30
Di-isoamylamine, $C_{10}H_{23}N$	-138.6		
		-12.30	-12.27
Tri-isoamylamine, $C_{15}H_{33}N$	-200.1		
Aniline, C_6H_7N	-65.1		
		-12.40	-12.38
Methylaniline, C_7H_9N	-77.5		
		-12.00	-11.97
Ethylaniline, $C_8H_{11}N$	-89.5		
Methylaniline, C_7H_9N	-77.5		
		-12.20	-12.09
Dimethylaniline, $C_8H_{11}N$	-89.7		
Azobenzene, $C_{12}H_{10}N_2$	-116.0		
		-12.35	-12.27
Azotoluene, $C_{14}H_{14}N_2$	-140.7		
Amidoazobenzene, $C_{12}H_{11}N_3$	-123.3		
		-12.40	-12.38
Amidoazotoluene, $C_{14}H_{15}N_3$	-148.1		
Nitrobenzene, $C_6H_5NO_2$	-64.1		
		-11.90	-11.88
1:2-Nitrotoluene, $C_7H_7NO_2$	-76.0		

TABLE V.
Acetylenic compounds.

		Pascal's value	Corrected value.
		$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$.	$\chi_{CH_2} \times 10^{-6}$.
Acetyl phenylacetylene, C ₁₀ H ₈ O	-86.9		
Propionyl "	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O	-99.0	-12.10
Butyryl "	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O	-110.9	-11.90
Valeryl "	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O	-123.9	-13.00
Caproyl "	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O	-135.6	-11.70

In Tables I—V, column 3 gives the value of CH₂-group calculated according to Pascal's atomic weights. In column 4 are given the values for the same group, when calculated with the aid of the now accepted atomic weights. The mean of all the values of column 3 yields a figure of -12.20 instead of -12.35 as given by Pascal for the first 24 substances examined by him. In column 4 the newer atomic weights reduce this to -12.17 × 10⁻⁶ which when corrected for water would yield a figure of -11.68.

From Perkin's observations on magneto-optical rotation and the data on viscosities and surface tension in relation to chemical constitution, it has been shown that in comparing physical properties for investigating chemical constitution, the first member of the homologous series generally leads to erroneous results. If we employ a similar procedure and reject the values for the first member in a series, the value for CH₂ comes even less than -11.68 and assumes a magnitude somewhat nearer to our value.

Recently Gray and Cruikshank (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 1421) mentioned to have obtained a value of -11.87 for a single CH₂-group from an investigation on three different homologous series of organic nitrites, nitrates and nitro compounds. The organic nitrites and nitrates were not investigated by us as they are difficult to obtain in a pure state, specially the aliphatic nitrites, on account of their tendency to decompose, particularly in glass vessels. Moreover, it is by no means certain that the organic nitrites do not show the tautomerism characteristic of HNO₂ metal derivatives. For example, it has not been definitely proved that a sample of methyl nitrate has no

nitromethane in equilibrium with it. Pascal in his numerous investigations on the susceptibilities of organic compounds has not included many of the nitro compounds and still less the nitrates and the nitrites. The only nitro bodies investigated by him were nitrobenzene and nitrotoluene and the difference in this case for a CH_2 -group is -11.90×10^{-6} which when corrected for the new value of water, is reduced to -11.42×10^{-6} , a figure quite in proximity with our value of -11.36×10^{-6} .

Further work on the subject is in progress.

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Preparation of Compounds Related to Phenacetin.

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This work was undertaken with a view to prepare substances related to phenacetin (I) particularly those containing an acetyl group in the ethoxy side-chain. The following were prepared:—

(1) β -Hydroxy-*p*-nitrophenetole (II, R=H). (2) β -Acetoxy-*p*-nitrophenetole (II, R=Ac). (3) β -Benzoyloxy-*p*-nitrophenetole (II, R=Bz). (4) β -Salicyloxy-*p*-nitrophenetole (II, R=Salicyl). (5) β -Chloro-*p*-nitrophenetole (II, where Cl takes the place of OR in the side-chain). (6) β -Hydroxy-*p*-acetylaminophenetole (I, R=H). (7) β -Acetoxy-*p*-acetylaminophenetole (I, R=Ac). (8) β -Hydroxy-*o*-nitrophenetole (9) β -Acetoxy-*o*-nitrophenetole. (10) β -Benzoyloxy-*o*-nitrophenetole. (11) β -Hydroxy-*m*-nitrophenetole.

(I)

(II)